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Intra-Family Conflicts and Sustained Operations of Family-Owned Businesses in the South-East, Nigeria

Author Details:

Christopher O. Nwonu

Department of Business Administration and Management, School of Business Studies, Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana nwonuchristophero@gmail.com; +234-8032600023

Abstract

This study examined the effect of intra-family conflicts on the sustained operations of family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. Descriptive survey method based on primary and secondary sources of data collection was adopted. Data was obtained from primary and secondary sources. Primary data was gathered through questionnaire while the secondary data was gathered from a review of several research publications, annual reports, articles, textbooks, unpublished thesis, journals and internet sources related family businesses. The study population consisted of 43,868 family-owned businesses. The sample size is 554 determined using Cochran (1963) statistical formula. Analyses were carried out using simple descriptive statistics organized and presented in tables, frequency and simple percentages. At the inferential level of statistical analyses, the hypothesis was subjected to double-test using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression. To establish whether an outcome is statistically significant, the researcher set up a 5% significance level while a 95% confidence level was applied and tested at 5% ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) alpha level. All analyses were carried out in SPSS 20.0. The study found intra-family conflicts affects sustained business operations significantly with r coefficient of 0.815 which is statistically significant with $t = 22.665$. Therefore, the study concludes based on the results above that intra-family conflicts significantly affects sustained business operations in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. The study recommends tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance and compromise, proper and effective management of conflicts, as strategies for resolving intra-family conflicts that can guarantee sustained operations.

Keywords: *Intra-family conflict, Sustained Operations and Family-owned Business*

Introduction:

Conflict is a situation of incompatible wishes, struggle, contest, unresolved differences, disagreements and irreconcilable desires which could affect the relationship and the achievement of common objectives. Intra-family conflicts, on the other hand, are conflicts involving siblings and members of the same family. This type of conflict has been identified as the most prevalent form of conflict in family-owned businesses in Nigeria and South-East, Nigeria in particular. Conflicts are not necessarily violent or negative, but rather inherent in all societies, and must be seen as a potential vector for change towards something positive (Kristina, 2009). Conflicts are the vital part of all organisations and conflict management is essential to solve the problems raised by conflict and to overcome the negative impacts of conflict (Ahmed, Nawaz, Shaukat & Usman, 2010; Anwar, Shahzad and Ijaz-ul-Rehman, 2012). Carlock and Ward (2001) state that all families experience relationship problems. Relationship conflicts such as children's desire to differentiate themselves from their parents, marital discord, or ownership dispersion among family members are central to every family (Eddleston & Kellermanns, 2007; Nosé, Korunka, Frank & Danes, 2015). However, family businesses face even bigger challenges and are

fertile grounds for conflicts (Harvey & Evans, 1994a; Sorenson, 1999) because family and business are interconnected. So, the potential for conflict is greater than in firms with other governance forms (Danes, Rueter, Kwon, & Doherty, 2002; Lee & Rogoff, 1996). Conflict in family businesses is a double-edged sword that can have positive or negative effects on the business. On one hand, conflict is described as bad and detrimental, and on the other, it can be beneficial in the sense that it can motivate a system to change (Frank, Keßler, Nosé, & Suchy, 2011; Nosé, et al., 2015).

Thus, this type of conflict occurs in a family unit. Sociologists would describe this as intra-unit conflict. In most cases, these conflicts arise from crisis occasioned by familial roles, expectations and role conflict. Examples include father-son, mother-father, husband-wife, brother-sister conflict. It may also imply cousin-cousin, nephew-uncle, sister-in-law or brother-in-law conflict. Such conflicts may be caused by such factors as simple as rudeness, claim to seniority, laziness, truancy at school, lying; to such extreme cases as land, property, inheritance and will dispute (Sheriff). The conflict has a life of its own (O'Neill, 1986; Wall & Callister, 1995). Conflict is said to exist when two or more groups engage in a struggle over values and claims to status, power and resources in which the aims of the opponents are to neutralise, injure or eliminate the rivals (Jeong, 2000). The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of intra-family conflicts on sustained operations of family-owned businesses in the South-East. Nigeria. To achieve the research objective, one question and hypothesis was formulated for the study.

Literature Review:

In the context of family business, Efendy, Zolin and Chang (2013) states that several studies show that conflict in the business could affect: individual well-being, such as satisfaction with family life (Danes, et al., 2000) and satisfaction with spouse (Amarapurkar & Danes, 2005); family relationships/harmony (Merwe & Ellis, 2007); and business performance (Eddleston & Kellermanns, 2007; Kellermanns & Eddleston, 2007). Conflicts are one of the important parts of organisational life. The main parties to the conflict are always the human part of the organisation. These individuals are the most important asset of the organisation, as managing other resources is not possible without the proper utilisation of the human resource. Human resource/s cause conflicts when they interact (Ishfaq, Muhammad, Muhammad & Ahmad, 2010).

The conflict also has been described as “awareness on the part of the parties involved of discrepancies, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires” (Jehn & Mannix, 2001; Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). Conflict is a process in which one party perceives that its interests are being opposed or negatively affected by another party (Wall & Callister, 1995). It is a process in which one party perceives that its interests are being opposed or negatively affected by another party (Wall & Callister, 1995). Intra-family conflicts, on the other hand, are conflicts involving siblings and members of the pathological family over disagreement, discrepancies, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires, unmet needs and desires to fully satisfy wants. Family conflict constitutes a key issue influencing the sustainability of family businesses. There are many family business failures in Nigeria, especially at the demise of the owner/founder (Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). The bulk of family-owned businesses intends to pass the control of the business to the next generation of family members. However, such family members are not always gifted with the skills required for the operation and management of the businesses (Merwe, 2009; Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). Thus, managing the intra-family conflicts is critical to the sustained operations and by extension, a succession of the family-owned business. Succession ensures the continuity of any family-owned business (Singhry, 2010; Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). Adedayo and Ojo (2016) observes that in polygamous families, nepotism, favouritism, lack of trust and respect among siblings, etc can create conflict thereby affecting the business. Hence, an effectively developed intra-family conflict provide for a succession plan and a smooth transition in management and ownership.

In order to ensure a smooth transition from the owner/founder to the successor, the need to guide against conflict within the family business is important (Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). Conflict management is a special concern for those in family businesses for maintaining long-term viability (Kaye, 1991; Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). Constructive conflict can drive the family business system toward its objectives, whereas sustained and/or unaddressed conflict can mire the system (Ward, 2006; Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). Planning for change may not occur because of conflicts within the business (Kaye, 1991; Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). Too much conflict can

threaten the survival of the family business or the family itself; family members may leave the business, diminishing its capacity, or a needed change may not be made within the business at a crucial regeneration point (Adedayo & Ojo, 2016). From the catalogue of businesses that have gone under at the demise of their owners/founders, the major problem confronting Nigerian family business owner is the need to manage conflict that may arise while the owner is alive or dead. Due to the increased number of children in marriages, the choice of who to mentor or groom becomes difficult and therefore the choice of a successor becomes a problem. This no doubt affects the firm's survival beyond the owner/founder. Conflict when unresolved and handled effectively can affect the fabric of any family business, the need for proper management, as it crops up becomes important (Adedayo & Ojo, 2016).

Research has shown that managers can spend as much as 20% of their time resolving conflicts (Thomas & Schmidt, 1976; Russell, Herman, Marshall & Dina, 1999). If conflict levels are too high, an organisation can be rife with anger and hostility, making it difficult to coordinate even the simplest shared activities (Baron, 1991; Rahim, 1985; Robbins, 1974; Thomas, 1993; Wall & Callister, 1995; Russell, et al., 1999). Individuals may be harmed as well. For example, people who live and work in contentious environments report higher levels of stress (Cropanzano, Howes, Grandey & Toth, 1997; Russell, et al., 1999) and more psychological distress (Bergmann & Volkema, 1994; Bolger & Schilling, 1991; Lepore, 1992; Russell, et al., 1999). This is because conflict is an important part of work life and needs to be managed effectively to promote the welfare of both organisations and the people who work in them. In large measure, organisations delegate to supervisors the responsibility for conflict management (Sheppard, 1984), although these individuals sometimes have inadequate conflict resolution skills (Russell, et al., 1999). The fact that managers often are called on to settle conflicts highlights the considerable need for research that can provide them with empirical guidelines (Russell, et al., 1999).

Ashwini (2014) states that literature on the conflict in the family business is largely based on conflict theories applied in organizational behaviour and management fields as well as in family business literature and thus, conflict studies are often done without much reference to a particular social or business context involved. The consequences or an outcome of the conflict is the least studied stage in the conflict process (Bergmann & Volkema, 1994; Ashwini, 2014). Individualistic nations tend to give priority to personal goals and preferences. Decisions are more likely to be evaluated based on how they influence individuals and less on how they influence the group (Russell, et al., 1999). Thus, Hofstede (1980) and Triandis (1996), the United States tends to be high on individualism and low on collectivism (Russell, et al., 1999). When resolving legal conflicts, individualistic societies protect the individual disputant by granting him or her influence in the procedure (Bond, Wan, Leung & Giacalone, 1985; Leung, 1987, 1988; Leung & Lind, 1986; Russell, et al., 1999).

Sources of Intra-Family Conflicts

Adedayo and Ojo (2016) list the following as some of the sources of intra-family conflicts which are mainly prevalent among Nigerian family businesses:

i. Polygamy: Rivalry between the siblings and spouses that follows the demise of a polygamous entrepreneur coupled with a variety of cultural laws guiding inheritance in Nigeria does not make for an objective selection of the best material as successor. Where a competent CEO material exists, he may not put his best to revamp or manage the family business. After all, it can later be taken from him by the elders and shared with other children.

ii. Nepotism: The employment of staff on the basis of personal relationships rather than due to qualification is more widespread in the family than in non-family businesses. Most family businesses are a mixture of people who have differing viewpoints based on their involvement in the different domains. As a result of family management, weaknesses arise, such as

- a. Nepotism instead of objective standards of employee hiring, evaluation, and reward, which then can cause conflict for those who are less involved;
- b. Conflicts between the interests of the family and the interests of the business as a whole;
- c. Lack of discipline over profits and performance in the organisation; and

- d. Failure to meet new business challenges in a timely manner (Gersick, Davis, Hampton & Lensberg, 1997).

It has been said that nepotism is the obvious way to destroy a family-owned business in a single generation. According to Ward (2006), “stories of family failure is quite common and known to all. The deleterious effects of nepotism are one example of such received wisdom”. In family businesses where the family system is dominant, the succession planning and process is often replete with nepotism or custom. In these firms, who will succeed to the helm of power is typically based on who is the eldest of the siblings or family relatives. In contrast, family businesses wherein the business system are dominant choose among those most prepared for the job. Sibling rivalry can pose another obstacle to smooth succession in cases where the retiring owner is transferring company leadership to more than one child. While some rivalries are inevitable, these must be managed so as not to impair business judgment or prevent collaboration from taking place. A wide variety of approaches such as enlisting one of the retired owners’ trusted advisors or a very senior non-family manager as a mediator can prove successful in preventing rivalry from becoming destructive. As noted by Lansberg (1997) in the *Family Business Succession Handbook*, “What seems to matter more than the substance of conflict management techniques used by sibling groups are that some sort of functional process is put in place in which they all agree. The author also states that acknowledging rivalries openly and diffusing them with humour can help the successors to rise above them.

iii. The Entitlement Issue: Another challenge to family succession occurs when members of the next generation believe they are entitled to a future ownership/leadership role within the company. Succession planning experts caution and common sense dictates that this belief can spell disaster for the entire business if left unchecked. Many family businesses that have weathered succession have established specific criteria that family members must meet in order to assume a management role within the business. Earning a college degree and obtaining outside work experience are among the most common of these requirements. Research indicates that a commitment to the principles and practices of stewardship— the sense that the family business “is not a personal possession, but a trust that has been given to family members for safe-keeping and for which they have deep caring and respect” is critical to the success of the succession process. The practice of stewardship begins with the business owner, who must model the attitude that business ownership is a privilege and not a right.

Conflict Management Styles/Conflict Handling Styles

Rahim (1983, 1986a, 2001) defines styles of handling conflict as integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding and compromising. Rahim’s (1986a) idea that organisational participants must learn the five styles of handling conflict to deal with different conflict situations effective (Kim, 2008). Efendy, Zolin, & Chang (2013) writes that a lot of studies have been conducted to examine conflict handling styles used by organisation/team members and their relationship with some factors, such as individual characteristics (gender, age, educational background, personality) (Moberg, 2001; Thomas & Thomas, 2008), culture (Kim, Wang, Kondo, & Kim, 2007; Posthuma, White, Dworkin, Yánez, & Swift, 2006), and hierarchical level in organisation (Rahim, 1986; Weider-Hatfield & Hatfield, 1995). For example, Weider-Hatfield and Hatfield (1995) tested the relationship between conflict handling styles and the level of intrapersonal, intragroup, and intergroup conflict in three different relationships – with supervisors, with subordinates, and with peers. The findings show that the level of conflict intensity experienced by an individual was affected by the styles of handling conflict used, e.g., subordinates using a high-obliging style with supervisors reported experienced more interpersonal conflict. A study by Sorenson (1999) found that collaboration styles produced positive outcomes for both the business and the family. The results of the study also show that accommodation and compromise strategies were not significantly associated with business success, but with positive family outcomes (Efendy, Zolin, & Chang, 2013). The five conflict styles that emerge from various combinations of these two dimensions are described below:

i. Integrating Style: High concern for self and others reflects openness, exchange of information, and examination of differences to reach an effective solution acceptable to both parties. The integrating style concentrates on problem-solving in a collaborative manner. Individuals with this style face conflict directly and try to find new and creative solutions to problems by focusing on their own needs as well as the needs of others

(Kim, 2008). Lawrence and Lorsch (1967) found the problem-solving (integrating) style to be more effective than other styles for attaining integration of the activities of different subsystems. When the issues are complex, this style is suitable for utilising the skills and information possessed by different parties to formulate solutions and successful implementations (Kim, 2008). Thus, the integrating style is believed to be both effective and appropriate in managing conflicts and, therefore, is perceived as highly competent. The integrating style is competent because it provides each disputant with access to the other persons' perceptions or incompatible goals, thereby enabling them to find a solution that integrates the goals and needs of both parties (Tutzauer & Roloff, 1988; Kim, 2008).

ii. Obliging Style: Low concern for self and high concern for others style is associated with attempting to play down the differences and emphasising commonalities to satisfy the concern of the other party. Obliging is associated with accommodating behaviors that include putting aside one's own needs to please the partner, passively accepting the decisions the partner makes, making yielding or conceding statements, denying or failing to express one's needs, and explicitly expressing harmony and cooperation in a conflict episode (Hocker & Wilmot, 1998; Kim, 2008). These types of conflict strategies are indirect and cooperative (Blake & Mouton, 1964; Kim, 2008). It can be used as a strategy when a party is willing to give up something with the hope of getting something in exchange from the other party when needed (Kim, 2008).

ii. Dominating Style: High concern for self and low concern for others style has been identified with win-loss orientation or with forcing behaviour to win one's position. The dominating style relies on the use of position power, aggression, verbal dominance, and perseverance. This style is direct and uncooperative (Blake & Mouton, 1964; Kim, 2008). Within interpersonal context, the dominating (competing/distributive) style has been found to be associated with low levels of effectiveness and appropriateness. However, Papa and Canary (1995) suggested that the dominating style might be somewhat effective in organisational contexts when there are production-related goals (Kim, 2008). In this case, an individual might use power strategies and aggression to effectively accomplish a goal, even though these strategies may be seen as inappropriate at a relational level (Kim, 2008). Spitzberg, Canary and Cupach, (1994) term dominating style as the maximising response to conflict, because it maximises the importance of one's own needs at the expense of the other individual's needs. Therefore, the dominating style may be seen as effective but not appropriate (Kim, 2008).

iii. Avoiding Style: Low concern for self and others style has been associated with withdrawal, buck-passing, or sidestepping situations. An avoiding person fails to satisfy his or her own concern as well as the concern of the other party. This style is useful when the issues are trivial or when the potential dysfunctional effect of confronting the other party outweighs the benefits of the resolution of conflict (Kim, 2008).

iv. Compromising Style: Intermediate in concern for self and others style involves give-and-take whereby both parties give up something to make a mutually acceptable decision. It may mean splitting the difference, exchanging concessions, or seeking the middle-ground position. It may be appropriate when the goals of the conflicting parties are mutually exclusive or when both parties, who are equally powerful, e.g. Labor and management, have reached a deadlock in their negotiation. This style may be of some use in dealing with strategic issues, but heavy reliance on this style may be dysfunctional (Kim, 2008).

Table 1: Conflict Handling Styles and the Situations Appropriate or Inappropriate

Conflict Styles	Situations where are Appropriate	Situations where are not Appropriate
Integrating	Issues are complex; synthesis of ideas is needed to come up with better solutions; commitment is needed from other parties for successful implementation; time is available for problem-solving; one part alone cannot solve the problem; and where resources possessed by different parties are needed to solve their common problems.	Task or problem is simple; the immediate decision is required; other parties are unconcerned about the outcome; and where parties do not have problem-solving skills.
Obliging	You believe that you may be wrong; issues are more important to the other party; you are willing to give up something in exchange for something from the other party in the future; you	Issues are important to you; you believe that you are right and; the other party is wrong or unethical.

	are dealing from a position of weakness and; preserving a relationship is important.	
Dominating	Issues are trivial; the speedy decision is needed; the unpopular course of action is implemented; necessary to overcome assertive subordinates; unfavourable decision by the other may be costly to you; subordinates lack the expertise to make to make technical decisions and; issues are important to you.	Issues are complex; issues are not important to you; both parties are equally powerful; decisions do not have to be made quickly and; where subordinates possess a high degree of competence.
Avoiding	Issues are trivial; potential dysfunctional effect of confronting the other party outweighs the benefits of resolutions and; cooling off period is needed.	Issues are important to you; it is your responsibility to make a decision; parties are unwilling to defer, issues must be resolved and; prompt attention is needed.
Compromising	Goals of parties are mutually exclusive, parties are equally powerful; consensus cannot be reached; integration or dominating is not successful and; the temporary solution to a complex problem is needed.	One party is more powerful and; the problem is complex enough needing a problem-solving approach.

Source: Rahim, M.A. (2002). Towards a Theory of Managing Organisational Conflict. *The International Journal of Conflict Management*, 13(3), 206-235.

Theoretical Framework:

The resource-based view (RBV) was adopted in this study as was first presented by Habbershon and Williams (1999). This theory assesses the competitive advantage of family firms. Habbershon and Williams (1999) identified familiness to be a bundle of resources that are distinctive to a firm as a result of family involvement (or system interaction between the family, its individual members and the business). In the resource-based view, the bundle of resources is identified as idiosyncratic to a particular firm in a particular environment. RBV asserts that firms are heterogeneous and that it is the idiosyncratic, immobile, inimitable, and sometimes in an intangible bundle of resources residing in the firm that gives the firm the opportunity for a competitive advantage and superior performance. RBV examines the links between a firm's internal characteristics and processes and its performance outcomes (Habbershon & Williams 1999; Chrisman et al. 2005; Duh, 2010). Sirmon and Hitt (2003) argue that family firms evaluate, acquire, shed, bundle, and leverage their resources in ways that differ from those of non-family firms. They believe these differences allow family firms to develop a competitive advantage (Duh, 2010). Thus, families that acknowledge inherent views in this theory would not allow a conflict of any type to affect their business.

Empirical Review:

Komala (2013) investigated the complexity of the conflicts in family top management teams and in particular the dimensions of the conflicts and their escalation. The population were selected from large-size family businesses in Indonesia. This study used the qualitative approach to critical incident technique (CIT) which required participants to recall intra-familial conflicts they have experienced which were significant to them. The intention was to generate rich descriptions of what the participants subjectively experienced, and then to classify their experiences into meaningful and useful patterns. This study collected data from individual and group interviews with 23 family and non-family employees of six large-scale privately-held family businesses in Indonesia. The study found that the family and the business are inextricably linked. Also, multi-generational family firms, inter-generational conflicts are more often than intra-generational conflicts. The study also found that some family members from the younger generation used a dominating strategy and experienced overt conflict with their seniors. The study concludes that the involvement of senior generations in business operations, the generational differences, and the perception gaps between generations could be antecedents of inter-generational conflicts.

Adedayo and Ojo (2016) examined how family conflict affects the sustainability of family business after the owner/founder has passed away. This study investigated the factors that created conflicts and how they affect the sustainability of family businesses in Lagos and Ogun States of Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design with a population of study limited to the family business owners who are members of the National Association

of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME). A stratified sampling technique was used to select the family businesses, from where a random sample of 327 was selected. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression were used to analyse the data. The results revealed that there was a strong positive correlation between family conflict and firm's sustainability, with an r value of correlation coefficient of 0.86. The study concluded that family business owners need to understand that their valued family business may not survive the next generation if they do not get serious about managing potential conflict that may arise. The study recommended that owners of family businesses must put in place structures that will ensure that potential conflicts can be resolved amicably after their exit without affecting the sustenance of the family business. Also, the owner/founder should avoid and do away with nepotism in the choice of a successor and the succession plan must reflect a true management succession. Hence, the founder must as a necessity, appoint a board of trustee if he suspects that problems may occur after his exit.

Nosé, Korunka, Frank, and Danes, (2015) examined how family climate counteracts the constraints in the business system created by relationship conflict that is known to negatively affect business outcomes (firm satisfaction and firm performance). The study used multiple measures of business outcomes that contribute to a deeper insight into dynamic processes within family businesses. Cross-sectional self-reported data were obtained from a nationally representative sample of 392. The study found negative effects of relationship conflict on firm satisfaction and firm performance. Adaptability was significantly related to firm performance. Cohesion and adaptability moderated the negative effect of relationship conflict on firm satisfaction; adaptability moderated the negative effect of relationship conflict on firm performance.

Methodology:

The design adopted for this study is a descriptive survey method based on primary and secondary sources of data collection. The data for this study was obtained from primary sources otherwise known as field survey and secondary sources otherwise called desk survey. Primary data was gathered through a structured questionnaire. The objective was to gather related, rich, detailed and specific information used in the analyses and to confirm, corroborate, dispute, reject or establish new facts or truth. The secondary data was gathered from a review of several research publications, annual reports, articles, textbooks, unpublished thesis, journals and internet sources related to organization structure and family businesses. The study population consist of registered and unregistered family-owned businesses in Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and the Imo States. A pilot study conducted by the researcher indicates there are about 43,868 family-owned businesses in the South-East. Cochran (1963) statistical formula was used to determine the sample size that gives 554. To ensure that the sample size determined above truly represent each State, a stratified random sampling technique was adopted using Bowley's proportional allocation statistical technique. The survey instrument was developed on the basis of information required to examine the research objectives of the study and composed of structured questionnaire divided into two parts namely Part A and Part B. Part A provides general information about the respondents while Part B focuses on the research questions broken into item questions to elicit responses from the respondents about their businesses. Likert scale grading format was used in designing the questionnaire. To ascertain the validity of the research instrument, the researcher subjected the instrument to face, construct, contents and response validations. To test the reliability of the research instrument, a pilot study was carried out to ensure that the items in the questionnaire were stated in clear terms without ambiguity with the same meaning to all the respondents. In order to measure internal consistency, Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to test the reliability of responses by the 25 respondents. The result shows that the Cronbach's Alpha of $0.84 > 0.70$ was achieved. This implies that the reliability of the test instrument was very high and reliable too. The study analyses made using simple descriptive statistics organized and presented in tables, frequency and simple percentages to calculate, analyse, show and summarize the responses of the respondents and the research question in a meaningful way. At the inferential level of statistical analyses, the hypothesis was subjected to double-test using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression to determine their statistical significance or otherwise. To establish whether an outcome is statistically significant, the researcher set up a 5% significance level. This implies that the researcher accepted a statistical significance occurring 5 times out of 100 (5/100) by chance. Thus, a 95% confidence level was applied and tested at 5% (p-

value ≤ 0.05) alpha level. The maximum acceptable risk of making type 1 error (rejecting the null hypotheses (H0) when it should have been accepted) is 5%. Hence, the decision rule adopted in this study is to reject the null hypotheses where the calculated p-value at 5% significance level with the respective degrees of freedom is greater than the critical or table value, otherwise, the null hypotheses should be accepted. However, using the probability value (p-value) produced from the SPSS software, the decision rule was to reject the null hypotheses if the probability value was less than the chosen 5% alpha level otherwise, accepted.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 2: Administration and Return of Questionnaire

	Returned (R)	536	96.8	96.8	96.8
Valid	Not Returned (NR)	18	3.2	3.2	100.0
	Total	554	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 2 above shows that a total of five hundred and fifty-four (554) questionnaire was printed and administered to the respondents by the researcher. The breakdown shows that five hundred and thirty-six (536) representing a response rate of 96.8% were returned while eighteen (18) questionnaire representing a non-response rate of 3.2% were not returned.

Table 3: Abia State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	137	95.1	95.1	95.1
Valid	Not Returned (NR)	6	4.2	99.3
	Not Properly Filled	1	.7	100.0
	Total	144	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 3 above shows a total of one hundred and forty-four (144) questionnaire distributed to respondents in Abia State, South-East, Nigeria. The table also shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected. A look at the table shows that one hundred and thirty-eight (138) questionnaire were returned out of one hundred and forty-four (144) distributed. This represents a 96.7% response rate. It further shows that one hundred and thirty-seven (137) were adjudged good for analyses representing 95.1%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 0.7% while six (6) questionnaire was not returned representing 4.2%.

Table 4: Anambra State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	126	96.9	96.9	96.9
Valid	Not Returned (NR)	3	2.3	99.2
	Not Properly Filled	1	.8	100.0
	Total	130	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 4 above shows that a total of one hundred and thirty (130) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Anambra State, South-East, Nigeria. It shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected. A look at the table shows that one hundred and twenty-seven (127) questionnaire were returned out of one hundred and thirty (130) distributed. This represents a 98.6% response rate. A further breakdown shows that one hundred and twenty-six (126) were adjudged good for analyses representing 96.9%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 0.8% while two (2) questionnaire was not returned representing 2.3%.

Table 5: Ebonyi State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	93	98.9	98.9	98.9
Valid Not Returned (NR)	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
Total	94	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version

The table 5 above shows that a total of ninety-four (94) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Ebonyi State, South-East, Nigeria. A look at the table above shows the breakdown of the questionnaire distributed and collected in Ebonyi State. The table shows that all the ninety-four (94) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents 100.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that ninety-three (93) was adjudged good for analyses representing 98.9% and one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.1%.

Table 6: Enugu State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	83	97.6	97.6	97.6
Valid Not Returned (NR)	1	1.2	1.2	98.8
Not Properly Filled	1	1.2	1.2	100.0
Total	85	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 6 above shows that a total of eighty-five (85) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Enugu State, South-East, Nigeria. The table equally shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected in Enugu State. It shows that eighty-four (84) out of eighty-five (85) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents a 99.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that eighty-three (83) were adjudged good for analyses representing 97.6%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.2% and one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.2% respectively.

Table 7: Imo State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	97	96.0	96.0	96.0
Valid Not Returned (NR)	2	2.0	2.0	98.0
Not Properly Filled	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	101	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 7 above shows that a total of one hundred and one (101) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Imo State, South-East, Nigeria. A look at the table above shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected in Imo State. The table shows that the ninety-nine (99) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents a 98.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that ninety-seven (97) was adjudged good for analyses representing 96.0% and two questionnaires were not properly filled representing 2.0% while another two were not returned representing 2.0% respectively.

Analyses of Research Objective:

How do intra-family conflicts with sustained operations of family-owned businesses?

Coded responses onTo what extent do intra-family conflicts affect sustained business operations of family-owned businesses?

Table 8 Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
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Intra-family conflicts affect sustained operations of the family businesses	533	4.144	1.1035
Sustained operations in family-owned businesses are one strategy that can help to ensure that the business survives	533	4.296	.8662
Intra-family conflicts do not affect sustained operations of family-owned businesses	533	1.989	1.2919
Sustained operations in family-owned businesses demand tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance, compromise where necessary, proper and effective management of conflicts, focus on success yet to be achieved and discipline in the face of c	533	3.754	1.2315
Intra-family conflicts in business are conflicts between siblings or members of the same family over a disagreement, differences, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires	533	3.674	1.3301
Valid N (listwise)	533		

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 8 above shows the mean score of each item question in the research question two. A calculation of the all the mean shows a grand total of 17.857 in all. A further breakdown shows a grand mean score of 3.9. Thus, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.5714 as calculated from the descriptive table above indicates that the extent to which intra-family conflicts affects sustained business operations of family-owned businesses is significant.

Table 9: Intra-family conflicts affects sustained operations of the family businesses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	7	1.3	1.3	1.3
Disagree	38	7.1	7.1	8.4
Undecided	65	12.2	12.2	20.6
Agree	222	41.7	41.7	62.3
Strongly Agree	201	37.7	37.7	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 9 above present results of responses of item question one in research question two that seeks to examine the extent to which intra-family conflicts affect sustained business operations of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is seven (7) representing 1.3%, thirty-eight (38) respondents of disagreeing represent 7.1% and sixty-five (65) of undecided representing 12.2%. However, two hundred and twenty-two (222) respondents agree to represent 41.7% and two hundred and one (201) respondents strongly agree to represent 37.7%. This implies that 8.4% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that intra-family conflicts affect the sustained operations of the family businesses. Similarly, 79.4% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that intra-family conflicts affect the sustained operations of the family businesses while 12.2% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 4.144 as shown in the descriptive table above indicates that intra-family conflicts significantly affects the sustained operations of the family businesses.

Table 10: Sustained operations in family-owned businesses is one strategy that can help to ensure that the business survives

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	21	3.9	3.9	3.9
Disagree	31	5.8	5.8	9.8
Undecided	156	29.3	29.3	39.0
Agree	183	34.3	34.3	73.4
Strongly Agree	142	26.6	26.6	100.0

Total	533	100.0	100.0
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Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 10 above present results of responses of item question two in research question two that seeks to examine the extent to which intra-family conflicts affect sustained business operations of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is twenty-one (21) representing 3.9%, thirty-one (31) respondents of disagreeing represent 5.8% and one hundred and fifty-six (156) of undecided representing 29.3%. However, one hundred and eighty-three (183) respondents agree to represent 34.3% and one hundred and forty-two (142) respondents strongly agree to represent 26.6%. This implies that 9.7% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that sustained operations in family-owned businesses are one strategy that can help to ensure that the business survives. Similarly, 60.9% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that sustained operations in family-owned businesses are one strategy that can help to ensure that the business survives while 29.3% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 4.296 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that sustained operations in family-owned businesses are one strategy that can help to ensure that the business survives.

Table 11: Intra-family conflicts does not affect sustained operations of family-owned businesses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	211	39.6	39.6	39.6
Disagree	237	44.5	44.5	84.1
Undecided	3	.6	.6	84.6
Agree	64	12.0	12.0	96.6
Strongly Agree	18	3.4	3.4	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 11 above present results of responses of item question three in research question two that seeks to examine the extent to which intra-family conflicts affect sustained business operations of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is two hundred and eleven (211) representing 39.6%, two hundred and thirty-seven (237) respondents of disagreeing represent 44.5% and three (3) of undecided representing 0.6%. However, sixty-four (64) respondents agree to represent 12.0% and eighteen (18) respondents strongly agree to represent 3.4%. This implies that 84.1% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that intra-family conflicts do not affect the sustained operations of family-owned businesses. Similarly, 15.4% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that intra-family conflicts do not affect the sustained operations of family-owned businesses while 0.6% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 4.296 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that intra-family conflicts affect sustained operations in family-owned businesses.

Table 12: Sustained operations in family-owned businesses demands tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance, compromise where necessary, proper and effective management of conflicts, focus on success yet to be achieved and discipline

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	3	.6	.6	.6
Disagree	9	1.7	1.7	2.3
Undecided	11	2.1	2.1	4.3
Agree	245	46.0	46.0	50.3

Strongly Agree	265	49.7	49.7	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 12 above present results of responses of item question four in research question two that seeks to examine the extent to which intra-family conflicts affect sustained business operations of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is three (3) representing 0.6%, nine (9) respondents of disagreeing represent 1.7% and eleven (11) of undecided representing 2.1%. However, two hundred and forty-five (245) respondents agree to represent 46.0% and two hundred and sixty-five (265) respondents strongly agree to represent 49.7%. This implies that 2.3% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that sustained operations in family-owned businesses demand tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance, compromise where necessary, proper and effective management of conflicts, focus on success yet to be achieved and discipline. Similarly, 95.7% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that sustained operations in family-owned businesses demand tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance, compromise where necessary, proper and effective management of conflicts, focus on success yet to be achieved and discipline while 2.1% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.754 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that for managers of family-owned businesses to achieve sustained operations, it demands tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance, compromise where necessary, proper and effective management of conflicts, focus on success yet to be achieved as well as discipline.

Table 13: Intra-family conflicts in business are conflicts between siblings or members of the same family over a disagreement, differences, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	41	7.7	7.7	7.7
Disagree	83	15.6	15.6	23.3
Undecided	14	2.6	2.6	25.9
Agree	207	38.8	38.8	64.7
Strongly Agree	188	35.3	35.3	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 13 above present results of responses of item question five in research question two that seeks to examine the extent to which intra-family conflicts affect sustained business operations of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is forty-one (41) representing 7.7%, eighty-three (83) respondents of disagreeing represent 15.6% and fourteen (14) of undecided representing 2.6%. However, two hundred and seven (207) respondents agree to represent 38.8% and one hundred and eighty-eight (188) respondents strongly agree to represent 35.3%. This implies that 23.3% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that intra-family conflicts in business are conflicts between siblings or members of the same family over a disagreement, differences, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires. Similarly, 74.1% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that intra-family conflicts in business are conflicts between siblings or members of the same family over a disagreement, differences, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires while 2.6% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.674 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that intra-family conflicts in business are conflicts between siblings or members of the same family over a disagreement, differences, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires.

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: Intra-family conflicts does not affect sustained operations of family-owned businesses

H₁: Intra-family conflict affects sustained operations of family-owned businesses

Table 14: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Intra-family conflicts	4.144	1.1035	533
Sustained operations in family-owned businesses	4.296	.8662	533

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 15: Correlations

		Intra-family conflicts	Sustained operations in family-owned businesses
Intra-family conflicts	Pearson Correlation	1	.919**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	533	533
Sustained operations in family-owned businesses	Pearson Correlation	.919**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	533	533

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 16: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.919 ^a	.844	.844	.3425	.844	2871.712	1	531	.000	.098

a. Predictors: (Constant), Intra-family conflicts

b. Dependent Variable: Sustained operations in family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 17: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	336.873	1	336.873	2871.712	.000 ^b
	Residual	62.290	531	.117		
	Total	399.163	532			

a. Dependent Variable: Sustained operations in family-owned businesses

b. Predictors: (Constant), Intra-family conflicts

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 18: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	1.308	.058		22.665	.000	1.195	1.421
	Intra-family conflicts	.721	.013	.919	53.588	.000	.695	.748

a. Dependent Variable: Sustained operations in family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

R = 0.919
R² = 0.844
F = 2871.712
T = 22.665
DW = 0.098

Interpretation and Decision: Table 8 shows the descriptive statistics of the relationship between intra-family conflicts and sustained operations in family-owned businesses. Intra-family conflicts have a mean score of 4.144 with a standard deviation of 1.1035, On the other hand, sustained operations have a mean score of 4.296 and a standard deviation of 0.8662. A careful observation of the standard deviation values reveals that there is almost the same variability of data points amongst the dependent and the independent variables. This implies that intra-family conflicts constitute about the same percentage of variables that significantly affect sustained operations in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. The regression sum of squares (336.873) in table 17 is greater than the residual sum of squares (62.290) which indicate that more of the variation in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistic (0.00) is less than 0.05 which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance.

R, the correlation coefficient which has a value of 0.919 indicate that there is a significant relationship between intra-family conflicts and sustained business operations in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. R square, the coefficient of determination shows that 84.4% of the variation in the business operations of family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria is explained by the model. With the linear regression model, the error of estimate is low with a value of 0.3425. The Durbin Watson statistic of 0.098 which is less than 2 indicates that there is no autocorrelation. The effect of intra-family conflicts on the sustained business operations coefficient of 0.815 indicates a significant effect between intra-family conflicts on the sustained business operations which is statistically significant with $t = 22.665$. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. Therefore, we conclude based on the results above that intra-family conflicts significantly affects sustained business operations in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The objective was to ascertain the effect of intra-family conflicts on sustained operations of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses of research question as earlier presented revealed that intra-family conflicts significantly affected sustained operations in family-owned businesses. The computed mean of the observed responses was 3.6 higher than the expected mean of 3.00 suggests that intra-family conflicts on sustained operations of family-owned businesses positively and significantly. Furthermore, hypothesis two was subjected to double test using both Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression to assess the effect of intra-family conflicts on sustained operations of family-owned businesses led to the rejection of null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternate hypothesis. Thus, the study concludes that a strong positive correlation exists between family conflict and firm's sustainability in the South-East, Nigeria ($r = 0.919$, $t = 22.665$, $F = 2871.712$ $p < 0.05$)

The above finding is in agreement with the study carried out by Ashwini (2014) titled "A Study of Conflict and its Impact on Family Managed Business: With Special Reference to Major Cities in Western Maharashtra". In the study, the analysis revealed that 45% respondents believed that businesses performed better after the split resulting from unresolved conflict among members in the family business as compared to when they were together. The study believed the split could serve as a frontier for the new family businesses to exploit growth opportunities.

Findings: This study made the following findings:

- i. That intra-family conflicts significantly affects the sustained operations of the family businesses.

- ii. That sustained operations in family-owned businesses are one strategy that can help to ensure that the business survives.
- iii. That for managers of family-owned businesses to achieve sustained operations, it demands tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance, compromises where necessary, proper and effective management of conflicts, focus on success yet to be achieved as well as discipline.
- iv. That intra-family conflicts in business are conflicts between siblings or members of the same family over a disagreement, differences, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires.

Conclusion and Recommendation: The study concludes that the extent to which intra-family conflicts affects sustained business operations of family-owned businesses is significant. The study recommends tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance and compromise, proper and effective management of conflicts, as strategies for resolving intra-family conflicts that can guarantee sustained operations.

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APPENDIX

Questionnaire

Instruction: The options to select are in the following scale. Please, indicate your opinion by shading below the number which matches your opinion in the table below:

- 5 = Strongly Agree (SA)
- 4 = Agree (A)
- 3 = Undecided (U)
- 2 = Disagree (D)
- 1 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

To ascertain the effect of intra-family conflicts on sustained operations of family-owned businesses					
Questions	SA	A	U	S	SD
a. Intra-family conflicts affect sustained operations of the family businesses					
b. Sustained operations in family-owned businesses are one strategy that can help to ensure that the business survives					
c. Intra-family conflicts do not affect sustained operations of family-owned businesses					
d. Sustained operations in family-owned businesses demand tolerance, efficient utilization of resources, endurance, compromise where necessary, proper and effective management of conflicts, focus on success yet to be achieved and discipline in the face of challenges					
e. Intra-family conflicts in business are conflicts between siblings or members of the same family over a disagreement, differences, incompatible wishes, or irreconcilable desires					